

TITLE

Customer Interaction Using Predicted Transaction Values

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FIELD OF RESEARCH STUDY: MANAGEMENT

Customer Interaction Using Predicted Transaction Values

Introduction:

In the present era of technology there are various ways to connect with the consumers across the globe and can possible to interact with them remotely twenty four by seven and may observe or predict the behavior of users on the basis of their transaction values and activities for the company products and services as they are using on regular basis for their purposes and here there is a liability of the company to take care of their subscribers or potential customers at a top priority because if the consumer is not happy with the products and services means that there is alarming situation for that company's growth hence the prediction of customer behavior or transaction is very important for the businesses growth.

Current Need of Customer Prediction:

In the present scenario of market and business all companies follow a best practices for their growth are feedback strategy and consume interaction policy because if consumers are happy with the services and facilities offered by any organization so there is great probability of success for that business and its simply means that the company understand the customer needs through prediction of the transaction values and succeed to meet the users requirements completely or at least 90 to 95%.

What Consumers wants from Company?

Following are the points which are required by the subscribers of an organization as given below:

- Empathy: As per user tendency, every consumer wants personal attention for their query and services provided by the company.
- Responsiveness: The user always seeks to get solution of their issue at top priority cause consumers do not want to be waited.

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Assurance: It is very important in any businesses because users want a kind of assurance for services or product as they are using.

- Reliability: Every customers want to good services always as the company committed to the users at the time of subscription therefore company should maintain the promise forever.

Objective:

- To identify the potential subscribers
- To increase the subscriptions using good strategies
- To grow the business with the consumer satisfaction

Versions of Interactions:

There are plenty of ways to increase the consumers using the prediction strategies on consumers.

- Through Ads on all medias like online and print
- If customer like the product or services as he saw during Ads would go to company store offline or online to explore more details about the same.
- It may be possible to subscribe the company newsletter.
- Consumer can call to customer care for more details.
- After predicting customer behavior company representative can call to users to support him or her.
- Either representatives can follow-up that users through email, calling.

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Fig1. Consumer Interaction

Tools Used:

Customer Interaction Management: It is a tool or kind of software used at companies to sense the user behavior or mood prediction and accordingly communicate with the customers which leads to make a success bond with the users which the consumer is available physical or on email, voice interaction.

Fig2. Consumer communication

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Used Prediction Policy:

According to the business philosophy there is a policy or kind of mostly used terminology is churn, this situation arises when consumers are not happy with the company's product or any services and stopped to use that services and product and join with other company services therefore consumer prediction is very important for any organizations growth.

Fig3. Consumer Churn Prediction Policy

- **Identify Loyal Consumers:**

Company should focus on the loyal users and track their journey since the beginning to till and when they stopped using services and when they call to SCM team for their issues so this is how can predict the users.

- **Take feedback of product and services:**

This is another way get predict the customer behavior about their services by taking the feedback time to time from consumers.

- **Are Subscriber satisfied with Services:**

This is also best practices used by the companies to know the customer satisfaction about services, products and support provided by the organizations to consumers.

Benefits:

- To know about quality of products
- To know about services when they failed at any point

• know about customer behavior and their needs

• know the gap between user and company

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To know point where the company is lagging

- To get the chance in improving the customer satisfaction and business growth

Conclusion:

The proposed solution towards the problem of statement customer interaction using predicted transaction values is stated and concluded that the consumer satisfaction and prediction of his or her behavior for product and services play a significant role towards the company growth.

References:

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- https://freshdesk.com/customer-interaction? tactic id=4237388&utm source=Google-AdWords&utm medium=Search-US-DSA-New&utm campaign=Search-US-DSA-New&utm term=&device=c&gclid=CjwKCAiAxp-ABhALEiwAXm6IydYM7d-NiS3ODkNyQjvoRgT4zJaFAYwFfDvZiWy3iUbcpGdLHvNvdRoCY00QAvD_BwE

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